

DIALECTICS BETWEEN SPIRITUALITY AND FREEDOM.

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Annotation. Freedom is one of the concepts that plays a big role in human life and affects the life of each person in different ways. This article analyzes the extent to which the liberalization of society, in particular, the liberalization of man, affects spirituality. The influence of forms of social consciousness on human freedoms has been studied.

Keywords. Spirituality, free citizen, public consciousness, liberalization.

“The issue of forming the spirituality of a free citizen, a free personality is the most urgent task”¹,- I.A. Karimov noted in his report dated April 14, 1999. Such attention to the development of our national spirituality is primarily aimed at ensuring the genuine freedom of every person. Because a person who is not self-aware cannot be bald and free, no matter how many opportunities and conditions you give him. But self-awareness means the ability to correctly determine one's attitude to one's Homeland, nation, humanity, and the reality of being, which is not easy to achieve.

In this regard, and Karimov noted that “assessing the processes of reform and renewal in Uzbekistan, I would like to note that the path to liberalization of all spheres of our life has essentially become the main link of all the changes taking place in our country”.²

Analyzing the process of liberalization of society from the point of view of its impact on the life of society and each person, it should be noted that this process, in the life of each person and society as a whole, manifests itself inconsistently. The fact is that freedom can affect a person's life in different ways. Free people can also have the opportunity to organize themselves. Freedom can also lead to a decrease in human feelings such as sociability, calculation with many. This, in turn, affects the spiritual world of a person. Not everyone can use freedom in their place, positively. Freedom can cause disorder, chaos both in society and in human life. Analyzing the different perceptions of freedom among members of society, Karl Popper argues that “an increase in the scale of freedom leads to a strong person imposing violence on a weak person”.³

¹ I.Karimov. “We are building our future with our own hands”. Tashkent. Uzbekistan. Works. Volume 7 p. 381

² I.Karimov. “The concept of further deepening democratic reforms and the development of civil society in our country”. Tashkent. Uzbekistan. 2010.

³ Karl Popper. “Open society and its enemy”. M.1992. p.89.

Human society, created by man, for this reason, relations and order in it are established primarily by man himself. How the society created by man and the various norms created by man in it affect the inner world and the spiritual being of a person also largely depends on the person himself. Even living in a slave-owning regime, a person can be spiritually, spiritually free, or even living in a free democratic society, a person cannot feel his freedom, use it properly.

Today, focusing on the social, economic, ideological and political picture of the world, one can observe an increase in instability and chaos in all these areas. In our opinion, the basis of all the states of chaos and instability observed in the above-mentioned spheres is human freedom, human free choice. "What humanity is capable of, its future fate cannot be predicted and predicted, because in the end everything will depend on its free choice". From the fact that a person always has freedom of choice, his spiritual and moral perfection comes to the surface.

"The process of liberalizing society is primarily a desire to improve relations between man and society"⁴, noted political scientist I. Ramazanov. Because in the process of liberalization in society, the relationship between a person and the state is coordinated. A free society is a society of humanity's dreams. As a result of the process of liberalization of society, an indissoluble relationship between a person and society arises. Because freedom is an essential, integral part of a person's spiritual being. Freedom is inherent in human thinking, psyche, will, morality, and the whole spiritual world. Since a free person lives in an unfree society, conflicts arise in his relations with society. Because if society denies human nature, then man denies society. In this society, a person cannot achieve happiness. For this reason, the process of formation of civil society, to which our state aspires, is directly accompanied by the process of liberalization of society.

As you know, man is a conscious being. There is a conscious need for it, there is creativity. To meet the needs, to engage in creativity, he needs knowledge, practical experience. For this reason, he has an interest, a desire to uncover the secrets of the world. He does not find his place in society only as a passive person who is being educated. He must constantly be in search, that is, in practical and mental, and if necessary, in scientific search, to engage in practical activities. He uses the gifts of nature not as they are, but recycles them at his discretion, creating them anew. A person differs from an animal in this feeling.

⁴ Ramazanov Mominov E. "Political Science". Tashkent. Justice. 1997. p.11

The human sense of creativity is based on certain knowledge. He draws knowledge from life practice and education throughout his life. As knowledge and experience grow, the circle of human communication and activity expands. This, in turn, increases the level of human freedom, expands the scope of his activities, and strengthens his creative potential. Knowledge and experience, first of all, reduce a person's direct dependence on nature and partly on the household, professional environment, increase his position in the team. In addition, in the process of development of society, it gave a person new opportunities, including increasing the level of his freedom. *A person with high knowledge and experience can take full advantage of the opportunities provided by society, while a person with a low level of knowledge cannot even exercise their rights. Applying this situation not to an individual, but to society as a whole, the problem manifests itself as the influence of the development of public consciousness and democratic freedoms, human rights on the rise of spirituality.*

The development of public consciousness is connected, on the one hand, with the material and economic development of society, and on the other – with the development of the education and upbringing system. Education and upbringing are complementary concepts. At this point, our first president I.A. Karimov's wise words should once again recall that education should not be separated from education, and education from education, that education is for us a matter of either life or death, or salvation, or destruction, or happiness.

Man is by nature a creature who loves beauty. Therefore, literature and art give him aesthetic pleasure. Encourages him to be creative. Therefore, in our state, great attention was paid to the development of cinema, theater, music, choreography, circus, fine and applied arts, and pop music. These works contribute to the development of artistic and ideological thinking of the people and increase their moral and artistic level. Not a single factor that has a positive impact on human consciousness and thinking is overlooked. Logistical, personnel and other necessary assistance is provided. Because, in the end, without the development of the human mind, thinking, people will not be able to sufficiently enjoy either the material heritage or the achievements of modern culture, it will be difficult for them to understand. For example, someone who does not know the old Uzbek language does not understand the works of Alisher Navoi well. For this reason, on the one hand, Navoi's works are adapted to the modern Uzbek language in prose or prose, and on the other hand, a dictionary of Navoi's works is compiled and other information about the old Uzbek language

is published. This expands the possibilities for independent reading and studying the works of Navoi and our other classics.

The improvement of the spiritual atmosphere in society prepares the ground for the growth of creative, creative abilities of a person. It leads to the growth of mutual trust, mutual assistance, kindness in society and in people. And in turn, the spiritual and cultural requirements imposed by society on a person are also becoming more diverse and increasing. Human rights (political, economic, etc.k.) guarantees the growth of his political, legal consciousness and culture. Democratic freedoms are growing. Free human activity in all aspects of society leads to the stabilization of political, moral, legal, economic (in general, in accordance with the forms of public consciousness) life of society. This means that under their influence, the spiritual life of society will consistently diversify, make up, and enrich itself. In the system of spirituality, there is a variety of human activities as a result of the increasing place of forms of social consciousness in the life of society, as well as their interaction. Human freedoms are increasing. This will ensure the further stabilization and development of spirituality as a system.

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